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ELECTRONIC PAPER TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

*Today's electronic displays have ever more evolved to be more lightweight, efficient and clear. Yet the importance of the paper has not diminished. We still prefer it to others for a variety of reasons including its readability, high contrast, convenient handling, minimum power requirement cost and strainless reading it offers. At the same time, an electronic display offers us a paperless environment and relieves us from carrying loads of paper for referring to information when required. **Electronic paper** and **e-paper** are display devices that mimic the appearance of ordinary ink on paper. E-paper comprises two different parts: the first is electronic ink, sometimes referred to as the “frontplane”; and the second is the electronics required to generate the pattern of text and images on the e-ink page, called the “backplane”. It is portable reusable storage and display medium that look like paper but can be repeatedly written one thousands of times. Electronic ink is a pioneering invention that combines all the desired features of a modern electronic display and the sheer convenience and physical versatility of sheet of paper. E-paper or electronic paper is sometimes called radio paper or smart paper. Electronic paper reflects light like ordinary paper and is capable of holding text and images indefinitely without drawing electricity or using processor power, while allowing the paper to be changed.*

Keywords : E paper, E- ink, portable, reusable.

E-PAPER TECHNOLOGIES

Electronic paper is said to be portable. Reusable storage and display medium that looks like paper but can be repeatedly written on (refreshed) by electronic means, thousands or millions of times. To build e-paper several different technologies exist, some using plastic substrate and electronics so that the display is flexible.

E-paper has the potential to be more comfortable to read than conventional display. This is due to the stable image, which does not need to be refreshed constantly, the wider angle and the fact that it reflects ambient light rather than emitting its own light. An e-paper display can read in direct sunlight without the image appearing to fade. The contrast ratio in available displays as of 2008 might be described as similar to that of newspaper, though newly developed implementations are slightly better. There is ongoing competition among manufactures to provide full color capability.

Cross-Section of Electronic-Ink Microcapsules

E Ink displays are also reflective, which means that the light from the environment is reflected from the surface of the display towards the user’s eyes, just like with traditional paper. Electronic paper screen reflects light from the environment and only consumes power when the content on it is changing, it is bistable and reflective. It will remain until you erase it, similar to a notebook, the content displayed on an EPD will hold a static image, even without electricity.

Electronic paper screen reflects light from the environment and only consumes power when the content on it is changing, it is bistable and reflective. It will remain until you erase it, similar to a notebook, the content displayed on an EPD will hold a static image, even without electricity.

It is just like flipping a coin, before it lands one can't predict heads or tails. Similarly the tiny particles of an EPD will either be reflective or non-reflective (that is, black or white). In practice this means that an EPD will be consuming power only when the content on it is changing. The rest of the time the display will simply show the image you want it to, This makes electronic paper extremely energy efficient, meaning that it can run for weeks on a single battery or even on alternative power sources, it provides a wider viewing angle than most other displays and making content displayed on e-paper perfectly visible even in direct sunlight.

E-paper comprises two different parts

- front panel
- back panel.

The first is electronic ink, sometimes referred to as the "FRONT PLANE", and the second is the electronics required to generate the pattern of text and images on the E-ink page called the "BACKPLANE".

Electronic ink(E ink)

E Ink is the creator of electrophoretic, also called as electronic ink — the optical component of a film used in Electronic Paper Displays (EPD). It utilizes the same pigments used in the printing industry today.

Although futuristic-sounding, electronic ink is actually a straightforward fusion of chemistry, physics and electronics.

There are two types of ink system

- two pigment ink system
- three pigment ink system

Two pigment

Electronic paper display is made up of millions of small capsules which are filled with a clear fluid containing tiny particles, with the particles each about as wide as a human hair. Each microcapsule contains black and white ink particles suspended in clear fluid. Negatively charged white pigments, positively charged are black pigments. When an electric field is applied, corresponding particles move to the top of the microcapsule where they become visible to the viewer. This makes the surface appear white or black at that spot.

Three pigment

E Ink also offers a 3-pigment ink system it makes use of microcup structure. it works similar to dual pigment system when a charge is applied to the pigments, and to a top and bottom electrode to facilitate movement. this system utilizes Microcups which are filled with the liquid and sealed instead of the use of microcapsules.

For the E Ink Prism film, we utilize different colored pigments from the standard black and white.

DIFFERENCES

1. ELECTRONIC AND PAPER DOCUMENTS

- An electronic data is created by several individuals than a paper documents.
- Electronic documents change faster, more frequently and easier than paper documents.
- The redundancy in electronic documents is higher than in paper documents.
- Electronic documents may be created by electronic means while paper documents are created by humans.

2. ELECTRONIC INK DISPLAY AND LCD

E - ink display

- It has a Wide viewing angle.
- Black on paper white
- Can be read in sunlight.
- It has plastic or glass sheets.
- Its thickness is nearly equal to 1mm.

Liquid Crystal Displays

- It has the Best image from only one position.
- It is Gray on Gray
- Which cannot be seen in sunlight.
- It requires power to hold the images.
- It uses Glass sheets only,
- Its thickness 7mm.

Applications of e-paper

E-paper will be used for applications such as e-books, electronic newspapers, portable signs, and foldable, rollable displays. Information to be displayed is downloaded through a connection to a computer ,Cellphones are starting to use the technology for their displays to created with mechanical tools such as an electronic "pencil".Electronic ink are also used in wristwatches and Amazon Kindle additions.The Motorola F3 uses an e-paper display instead of an LCD.

It is also used for Digital Photo Frame in order to overcome the problem of high quality, power supply and wide viewing angle,Electronic paper requires such small amounts of power that the image could remain for several months to years with a small battery pack.

Some devices, like USB flash drives, have used electronic paper to display status information,such as available storage space.Flexible display cards enable financial payment cardholders to generate a one-time password to

reduce online banking and transaction fraud.

Pros and Cons

Pros

- Paper like readability
- Ultra-Low power consumption
- It has high Clarity,which reduces eye strain,

- It contains multimedia information and also include graphics

Cons

- It has very low switching speed
- Its responses are slow to the changes
- Problems are faced in extreems temperatures humidity
- Its time consuming to run video

Conclusion

Today, paper remains the most popular document medium because of its ease of use, flexibility, portability, and compatibility which has made it difficult to replace. The e-paper can also communicate satellite and other computer easily. And for the further more updates the researchers are thinking of making a paperless world. Finally, there would be a more usage of E-paper technology rather than an LCD and an ordinary paper. The introduction of a new technology can simulate a synergy between old and new. We should reconsider the argument to completely replace all paper documents, and consequently, we predict a co-existence between paper and E-Paper.

References :

1. Adithya. Potu , R. Jayalakshmi , Dr. K. Umpathy ,(2016) , ”Smart Paper Technology a Review Based On Concepts of E-Paper Technology”, IOSR Journal of Electronics and Communication Engineering, e-ISSN: 2278-2834 , 11(1), 42-46.
2. Mythili. G. A. , Pavithrah. B. R. and Manjubhashni. S, (2016) , “E-Paper Technology”, International Journal of Trend in Research and Development ,ISSN: 2394-9333, 3(5).